

INTEGRATING NEUROLOGICAL EXAMINATION WITH RADIOLOGY DIAGNOSIS THROUGH ONTOLOGY

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Abstract: Nowadays integration of health information is facing many challenges. There is a need in different sectors or departments at the hospital to exchange information in order to offer better healthcare for the patient. This paper describes the integration process of radiology diagnoses and findings according to the neurological examination of the patient. Also, this ontology can be used in facilitating, exchanging knowledge, offering interoperability between these sectors and it is designed in a manner that can help in the decision-making process.

Key Words: ontology, neurology, radiology, mapping, integration, interoperability.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a need for exchanging information between medical sectors in the hospital in order to provide better healthcare for the patients. University Hospital Center "Mother Teresa" is the biggest hospital in Albania. For instance, in the neurology and radiology department, there is a need to facilitate, exchange patient information and knowledge between them. Neurologic patients may need to be imagery diagnostification in order for the doctor/physician to understand their health situation. The patient may take different neurological examinations, such as EEG, Long Term Video Monitoring (LTVM) or medication. After certain situations the patients may be sent to the radiology department in order to take resonance or scanner according to the health situation of each of them.

All the information about the patient is very important and it is needed in a very short time because of the situation of the patient. The neurology doctor first makes the neurologic examination of the patient and then may be needed for example the resonance from the radiology department in order to identify the exact diagnosis, treatment and provide better healthcare services for the patient. So, neurology and radiology are very connected to each other aiming at identifying the diagnoses of the patient in the hospital.

This research paper gives the solution to these problems by offering an ontology that will integrate neurological examination with the radiology diagnosis. This ontology can be used in:

- the decision-making process in order to provide better healthcare for the patients;
- writing health reports;
- as a dictionary providing synonyms for different diseases, symptoms, etc.;
- providing interoperability using SNOMED CT;

In this ontology we will reuse existing ontologies like NEO Ontology, GAMUTS Ontology and SNOMED CT.

This research paper is organized in 5 sections. Section 2 presents the state of the art. Section 3 analyses the methodology, section 4 presents the Ontology and in section 5 are the conclusions and our future work.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Using ontology in the medical domain offers the opportunity to efficiently manage various sources in this domain [1]. In this research, we were focusing on ontologies used in neurology, radiology, their application and their use in these fields.

Radiology Gamuts Ontology (RGO) is a knowledge model of differential diagnoses in radiology, diseases, interventions and imaging findings [2]. In [3] it is constructed as a decision support system for potential radiological diagnoses in response to one or more user-specified imaging observations. The GAMUTS ontology has been integrated with other ontologies like Orphaned Rare Disease Ontology [4], Disease Ontology and Human Phenotype Ontology [5], RadLex, SNOMED CT and ICD-10-CM [6].

TRIES ontology is the most important component of the TRIES system that is a system for information extraction that is designed to process free texts radiology reports in order to extract and convert the available information into a structured information model [7].

RadiO is a prototype application ontology for radiology reporting tasks, which aligns a controlled imaging vocabulary (RadLex) to a reference ontology for anatomy (FMA) in order to support the structured reporting of image observations and to build a knowledge base concerning how image entities are used in the process of diagnosing diseases [8].

Neurology Disease Ontology provides a formal foundation for the representation of clinical and research data pertaining to neurological diseases [9].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Main Ontologies and standards used in the Ontology

In order to maximize the integration of data using the ontology first we consider reusing other ontologies. In the ontology we have imported NEO and GAMUTS ontologies, as described at the state of art.

NEO (Neurological Examination Ontology) Ontology is an ontology describing neurological findings (signs and symptoms). It consists of 1273 classes, 1276 declaration axioms, 1262 logical axioms [10]. Radiology Gamuts Ontology (RGO) ontology as described at the state of art is an ontology of diseases, interventions, and imaging findings that was developed to aid in decision support, education, and translational research in diagnostic radiology [11].

In the Annotation Properties we can distinguish the relationships of the ontology to other ontologies or standards. The relationships of NEO and GAMUTS Ontology with other ontologies using sameAs axiom are shown in the figure above.

Figure 1. Relationships of NEO and GAMUTS Ontologies to other Ontologies

The NEO and the GAMUTS Ontologies are accessed using the BioPortal of the Center for Biomedical Ontology [12] [13]. The integration process between NEO and GAMUTS is done according to the ontology mapping. So the concepts of NEO will be mapped to the GAMUTS Ontology in order to gain knowledge from the *may_cause* and *may_caused_by* relationships.

SNOMED CT is the most comprehensive clinical terminology in use around the world in order to offer the integration and facilitate the exchange of clinical medical information. The advantages of using SNOMED CT range from increased opportunities for real-time decision support to more accurate retrospective reporting for research [14]. It has a hierarchical structure and includes clinical findings, anatomy, test findings, and morphological connections [15].

B. Linked data for the application ontology

According to the [16] mapping is the oriented, or directed, version of an alignment and it maps the entities of one ontology to at most one entity of another ontology. There are different tools and techniques used in matching and mapping the entities from one ontology to the other ontology.

In [17] the authors propose measures for describing the similarity of different ontology parts at the lexical and conceptual level. In the process of integrating the ontologies we will use a hybrid mapping as described below.

Identifier SNOMED CT is being used in both ontologies. SNOMED CT is the most comprehensive clinical healthcare terminology [18]. As we can see from figure 1 both

ontologies have used SNOMED CT (when it is possible). In NEO there is only the SNOMED CT code for the concept (for example 52008007) while in GAMUTS the whole URI. So the first step towards finding the mappings between these ontologies is by using SNOMED CT Code. The SNOMED CT codes are accessed from the URI in the GAMUTS Ontology and are compared to the SNOMED CT codes in NEO Ontology using SQL Server Database. In the table below are identified the same concepts in both ontologies using SNOMED CT code.

TABLE I Mappings using SNOMED CT

<i>GAMUTS Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Myoclonus	Myoclonus
Nystagmus	Nystagmus
Papilledema	Papilledema
Paraplegia	Paraplegia
Parinaud syndrome	Parinaud syndrome
Proptosis	Proptosis

The same concept can be expressed in different ways. In the table below are some of the concepts that have the same meaning.

TABLE II Mappings using SNOMED CT

<i>GAMUTS Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Alopecia	Baldness
blepharospasm_omandibular_dystonia	Meige syndrome
Pyrexia	Fever
Facial nerve paralysis	Facial paralysis
Miosis	Small Pupil
Microphthalmos	Nanophthalmos

But, it was impossible to find all matches using SNOMED CT code because the code was missing in either NEO or GAMUTS ontology.

According to [19] it has been done a lexical comparison between the list of the terms in NEO Ontology and the list of the terms in GAMUTS Ontology. The terms are enriched with synonyms when the synonyms were missing or with other synonyms. All the terms were

imported into SQL Server Database. After this process, each synonym class/concept from NEO Ontology is compared with the GAMUTS Ontology. Then all the matched terms are mapped to each other in the Protégé. Some of the mapped terms are illustrated in the above table.

TABLE III Mappings using synonyms

<i>GAMUTS Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Intellectual deficit	Mental retardation
Deafness	Hearing loss
Diabetes mellitus	Diabetes
Dysmorphic facies	Dysmorphic face

In table number IV is being illustrated some examples of the mapped terms that are found between two ontologies. They have the same terms used in the concept of the class but in different positions.

TABLE IV Mappings through changing the positions of the terms

<i>GAMUTS Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Optic ataxia	Ataxia optic
Oromandibular dystonia	Dystonia oromandibular
Essential tremor	Tremor essential
Ptosis bilateral	Bilateral ptosis
Weakness generalized	Generalized weakness
Pain neck	Neck pain

In the table below are illustrated some of the mappings that are done through comparing classes in terms of the similarity in NEO and GAMUTS Ontology.

Table V Mappings through similarity comparisons

<i>Gamuts Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Saccadic intrusion	saccadic intrusions
Horner syndrome	Horner's syndrome
cervical spine injury	injury of cervical spine

In the table below are illustrated some of the mappings that are done through removing words like left or right in the NEO Ontology.

TABLE VI Mappings through removing words

<i>Gamuts Ontology</i>	<i>NEO Ontology</i>
Eyelid ptosis	Ptosis left eyelid
Eyelid ptosis	Ptosis right eyelid
Proptosis	Right proptosis

IV. INTEGRATION THE ONTOLOGIES

As stated at the beginning of this paper, we will import NEO and GAMUTS Ontology in the new ontology. In order to save information on the origin URI of the following ontologies, we have created the relevant prefixes in Protégé. For example, for the <http://www.gamuts.net/entity#> URI we will create the gamuts prefix and the neo prefix for the <http://www.semanticweb.org/danielhier/ontologies/2019/3/untitled-ontology-57#> URI. In the Owl file of the ontology we can distinguish the terms/classes from the following ontologies and their relationships. In the example below the two terms, diabetes and diabetes_mellitus are mapped with each other using the sameAs annotation.

```
<AnnotationAssertion>  
  <AnnotationProperty IRI="sameAs"/>  
  <AbbreviatedIRI>neo:diabetes</AbbreviatedIRI>  
<AbbreviatedIRI>gamuts:diabetes_mellitus</AbbreviatedIRI>  
</AnnotationAssertion>
```

From the figure below we can distinguish the imported NEO classes used in the ontology. There are connected with the Patient class using the relevant object properties like has_symptom, has_headfinding, has_motor_finding etc.

Figure 2. The relationship of the patient class with neurological examination classes

After mapping the terms from NEO Ontology to GAMUTS Ontology, the doctor can found the may_cause and may_cause_by findings of a certain term using the knowledge from the Gamuts Ontology.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, it is proposed the integration between neurological examination of the patient (NEO Ontology) with the radiological diagnoses (GAMUTS Ontology) in order to offer interoperability between neurology and radiology departments by using SNOMED CT. Also the ontology describes the may_cause and may_cause_by findings (GAMUTS Ontology) in radiology according to the neurologic examination of the patients. This ontology can be used as a semantic dictionary for the neurological examination, common diseases in neurology and the related causes in radiology.

The ontology is designed in a way that it can help in easily sharing and gaining knowledge according to the patient's data. The records of the patients can be used in gaining more knowledge and relationships according to the signs, symptoms, causes or diseases.

As a future work of this research we will add neurological diagnoses and their relationships in the overall ontology.

VI. REFERENCES

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